

Assessment of coated monoliths for Direct Air Capture

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Abstract

Zinc-based Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) CALF-20 is a promising material for carbon capture due to its high CO₂ capacity and reduced water uptake. This study assesses the use of a monolith coated with CALF-20 to capture ultra-dilute CO₂ from air in order to contain the energy required to process large air flows through a contactor with reduced pressure drops. The monolith is designed taking into account the superficial velocity through the channels and the multicomponent adsorption of N₂, CO₂, and H₂O. Different desorption temperatures are analysed, showing the possibility to regenerate the monolithic adsorption bed with low temperature heat below 80 °C.

Keywords: Direct Air Capture, Carbon Dioxide, CALF-20, Monolith, Adsorption.

Introduction

It has been almost a decade since the 2015 Conference of Parties in Paris, where several countries set an ambitious goal to contain climate change by limiting global warming in below 2 °C. Despite the current efforts global temperature continues to rise each year, reaching its peak since the 19th century [1, 2]. Containing new emissions alone cannot revert the ongoing situation. The removal of CO₂ that is present in the atmosphere has become a mandatory measurement to reduce this gas concentration levels.

Direct Air Capture (DAC) is a promising negative emission technology (NET) that targets CO₂ removal from air by using reversible adsorption processes. In contrast to post-combustion carbon capture, DAC needs to capture ultra-dilute CO₂ (approximately 400 ppm in ambient air), compress and purify it to at least 95% by volume to be used in a downstream processes or stored underground [3]. The development of sorbent materials that have a high CO₂ working capacity and a small water uptake is one of the key requirements to enable a wider deployment of DAC. Several sorption-based DAC processes are heat-powered and low-temperature heat is preferable for regenerating the sorbent since it makes the process more economically attractive [4, 5], for the possibility to recover energy sources that would be otherwise wasted.

This work aims to evaluate the use of monoliths of CALF-20 for DAC. This Metal-Organic Framework (MOF) shows high CO₂ capacity, while maintaining some degree of hydrophobicity [6]. The use of coated monoliths as adsorption beds allow reduced pressures drops, less energy input and a closer contact between the gas and the adsorbent [7, 8].

Methodology

A plug flow isothermal mass balance was elaborated considering the following assumptions: (i) gas phase described by ideal gas law; (ii) equilibrium theory; (iii) negligible radial profiles; (iv) the bed was initially filled with pure nitrogen at 101.325 kPa and 298.15 K; (v) adsorption multicomponent equilibrium is described by the Ideal Adsorbed Solution Theory (IAST) [9]. Pressure drop model is reported in [10]. The overall and component mass balances are described in Equations 1 and 2.

$$\frac{\partial(u.C_T)}{\partial z} + \varepsilon_b \cdot \frac{\partial C_T}{\partial t} + (1 - \varepsilon_b) \cdot \rho_B \cdot \sum_i \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial(u.C_i)}{\partial z} + \varepsilon_b \cdot \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + (1 - \varepsilon_b) \cdot \rho_B \cdot \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where u (m/s) is the gas superficial velocity, C_T (mol/m³) is the total concentration in the gas phase, C_i (mol/m³) is the concentration of component i in the gas phase, ε_b is the external void fraction, ρ_B (kg/m³) is the particle density, and q_i (mol/kg¹) is the adsorbed amount of component i .

Air composition in feed is assumed to contain only N₂, CO₂ and H₂O, and all other atmospheric gases are lumped in N₂ concentration. Adsorption isotherms are described by Equations 3 to 5 [6].

$$q_{N_2} = q_{s1,N_2} \frac{b_{1,N_2} C_{N_2}}{(1+b_{1,N_2} C_{N_2})} \quad (3)$$

$$q_{CO_2} = q_{s1,CO_2} \frac{b_{1,CO_2} C_{CO_2}}{(1+b_{1,CO_2} C_{CO_2})} + q_{s2,CO_2} \frac{b_{2,CO_2} C_{CO_2}}{(1+b_{2,CO_2} C_{CO_2})} \quad (4)$$

$$q_{H_2O} = q_{s1,H_2O} \frac{b_{11,H_2O} C_{H_2O} + 2b_{12,H_2O} (C_{H_2O})^2 + 3b_{13,H_2O} (C_{H_2O})^3}{(1+b_{11,H_2O} C_{H_2O} + b_{12,H_2O} (C_{H_2O})^2 + b_{13,H_2O} (C_{H_2O})^3)} + q_{s2,H_2O} \frac{b_{2,H_2O} C_{H_2O}}{(1+b_{2,H_2O} C_{H_2O})} \quad (5)$$

Where $q_{s,i}$ (mol/kg) is the saturation capacity (of site n) and b_i (m³/mol) is the adsorption equilibrium constant (of site n). The values of those parameters are reported in Table 1. The parameter b (m³/mol) is dependent of temperature following Equation 6.

$$b_i = b_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta U_i}{RT}\right) \quad (6)$$

Table 1: Pure components isotherm parameters [6]

Parameter	Value	Unit	Parameter	Value	Unit
N₂ isotherm			H₂O isotherm		
q_{s1,N_2}	5.6583	mol/kg	q_{s1,H_2O}	1.6290	mol/kg
b_{01,N_2}	8.143×10^{-7}	m ³ /mol	b_{011,H_2O}	-2.685×10^{-17}	m ³ /mol
ΔU_{N_2}	-17.96×10^3	J/mol	b_{012,H_2O}	1.158×10^{-16}	(m ³ /mol) ²
CO₂ isotherm			b_{013,H_2O}	5.374×10^{-17}	(m ³ /mol) ³
q_{s1,CO_2}	2.3870	mol/kg	$\Delta U_{1,H_2O}$	-97.99×10^3	J/mol
b_{01,CO_2}	5.519×10^{-7}	m ³ /mol	q_{s2,H_2O}	5.7810	mol/kg
$\Delta U_{1,CO_2}$	-35.06×10^3	J/mol	b_{02,H_2O}	8.773×10^{-12}	m ³ /mol
q_{s2,CO_2}	3.2711	mol/kg	$\Delta U_{2,H_2O}$	-64.72×10^3	J/mol
b_{02,CO_2}	5.187×10^{-8}	m ³ /mol			
$\Delta U_{2,CO_2}$	-28.95×10^3	J/mol			

The process cycle was characterized by two steps: adsorption and desorption. A twin-bed system was assumed in phased cycle design, synchronizing the adsorption of one bed the desorption of the other. Initially, ambient air is fed to the contactor bed until it is saturated with CO₂. After that, part of the clean air produced in the twin-bed is heated and fed counter-currently to purge the system. Boundary conditions used in the model are described in Table 2. The mathematical model was implemented in gPROMS software [11] to solve the system of partial differential and algebraic equations. The system was discretized in 50 axial nodes and with a tolerance of 10⁻⁵.

Table 2: Boundary conditions for adsorption and desorption steps

Adsorption		Desorption	
$C_{i,(z=0)} = C_{i,ads}$	$\left. \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial z} \right _{z=L} = 0$	$\left. \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial z} \right _{z=0} = 0$	$C_{i,(z=L)} = C_{i,des}$
$\left. \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right _{z=0} = 0$	$P_{(z=L)} = P_{atm}$	$P_{(z=0)} = P_{atm}$	$\left. \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} \right _{z=L} = 0$
$u_{(z=0)} = \frac{\dot{V}_{ads}}{A}$	$\left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right _{z=L} = 0$	$\left. \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right _{z=0} = 0$	$u_{(z=L)} = \frac{\dot{V}_{des}}{A}$

where \dot{V} ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) is the gas volumetric flowrate, and A (m^2) is the cross-sectional area, P is the pressure and P_{atm} is the atmospheric pressure (101.325 kPa). Axial position is represented by z and varies from 0 to L , where L (m) is the length of the adsorption column. The subscript i refers to the component (N_2 , CO_2 , and H_2O). The subscription 0, *ads* and *des* refer to the feed, adsorption, and desorption step, respectively.

A cordierite monolith (200 CPSI, 0.20 mm wall thickness, 60% wall porosity) was assumed as a support for the coating layer. Due to the high porosity of the wall of the monolith, we considered the monolith pores filled of adsorbent. The mathematical model described in this section was applied to each individual monolith channel. Multiple coating layer thicknesses were analysed to evaluate adsorption time and adsorption capacity. The monolith size was defined using the CO_2 adsorption capacity at the feed conditions in a multicomponent adsorption.

An air stream of $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ at ambient conditions (101 kPa, 298 K) containing nitrogen, carbon dioxide and water was used to feed the coated monolith. Air had a fixed CO_2 composition of 400 ppm and 1% relative humidity (RH). Different regeneration temperatures were investigated at a given air flowrate to allow adsorption and desorption steps to be similar in duration. The analysis was performed considering only equilibrium, given reliable kinetic data of the multicomponent mixture on CALF-20 are not available yet.

Results and Discussion

Bed sizing and dynamic of the adsorption step

Understanding the adsorbent working capacity is essential to size the adsorption bed. Although IAST over-predicts the water content in CALF-20 at low water concentrations, the competitive adsorption of CO_2 can be well described for relative humidity below 40% [6]. Therefore, at 298 K and 101.32 kPa, each gram of empty CALF-20 can capture 0.028 mmol of CO_2 . This means that, if adsorption lasts for 1 minute, at least 10 g of adsorbent are required to capture 400 ppm of CO_2 from an air stream of $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$.

The monolith diameter was calculated by the superficial velocity in each channel. For packed beds, typical gas superficial velocities are $0.1\text{--}0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, but in monoliths this value can go up to $2\text{--}3 \text{ m/s}$ [12]. A value of 1 m/s was chosen to reduce pressure drop and control residence time for a better contact between the gas and the adsorbent. To ensure that the superficial velocity in each channel does not exceed this value, the monolith was designed with a diameter of 2.5 cm.

Lastly, the monolith length was calculated as a function of the coating thickness. Typical thicknesses in range of $20\text{--}100 \mu\text{m}$ [13] were analysed and a monolith with 20 cm length and a coating layer with $50 \mu\text{m}$ was assumed. A breakthrough curve was calculated to evaluate the duration of the actual adsorption step, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Dynamic column breakthrough for CALF-20 at 298 K and 101 kPa in a monolith channel. C_i (mol/m^3) is the gas concentration of component i at $z = L$. $C_{i,0}$ (mol/m^3) is the component concentration of the feed gas. For N_2 , CO_2 and H_2O values of $C_{i,0}$ are $40.845 \text{ mol}/\text{m}^3$, $0.016 \text{ mol}/\text{m}^3$, and $0.013 \text{ mol}/\text{m}^3$, respectively.

Among the three components, nitrogen is the least strongly adsorbed, followed by CO_2 , and lastly, we can observe that water breakthroughs at around 160 s. As the desired component in DAC is CO_2 , the adsorption can be terminated after it reaches saturation throughout the monolith (after 70 s). The concentration change between 70 and 180 s does not justify extending the adsorption step for 110 more seconds.

Despite being the least strongly adsorbed component, nitrogen has the highest concentration in the gas phase. Therefore, N_2 has a larger loading on the adsorbed phase. Figure 2 shows the concentration profile of the adsorbed phase distributed along the length of the column at the end of the adsorption. For the conditions simulated, pressure drop across the monolith was below 30 Pa.

Fig. 2. Adsorbed amount profile in the monolith channel at the end of the adsorption (70 s).

Desorption Temperature

Recovery of the adsorption material needs a driving force to move the system to a new equilibrium. This can be done by a change in pressure, such as in Pressure Swing Adsorption, or by increasing the temperature. A combination of those can also occur, but this work limits the analysis to Temperature Swing Adsorption (TSA) only.

To simplify the initial analyses, we considered that the heating and cooling steps are instantaneous between the air and the coated layer (thermal equilibrium). Three desorption temperatures were then evaluated: 50 °C, 60 °C and 70 °C, all of them below the state-of-the-art desorption temperature (around to 80 °C) for similar processes [5]. The water concentration was kept at 1% RH.

A fraction of clean air produced by the twin column (during the adsorption step) was fed at the product end ($z = L$) of the contactor bed. The purge flowrate was adjusted for each temperature to obtain a duration of 70 s. For the temperatures of 50 °C, 60 °C and 70 °C, desorption flowrates were assessed as 0.28 m³/h, 0.21 m³/h and 0.14 m³/h, respectively.

Fig. 3. Gas phase mole fraction for N_2 , CO_2 and H_2O at $z = 0$. Results for different desorption temperatures of 50 °C (—green), 60 °C (—red), and 70 °C (—blue).

For the lowest temperature, water is desorbed almost at constant concentration during all the purge extent. By increasing desorption temperature, as it can be seen in Figure 3, water is more easily desorbed, migrating from the adsorbed phase to the gas phase. When the column is desorbed at 50 °C, water and CO₂ concentrations are similar (0.046 mol/m³ for CO₂ and 0.049 mol/m³ for H₂O) along the purge. This profile changes with the increase of desorption temperature. Both H₂O and CO₂ show a raise in concentration in the gas phase. However, water is more sensitive to this increase, desorbing faster than CO₂. For the highest desorption temperature, at 70 °C, all water is desorbed in half of the time for CO₂ desorption.

For all three temperatures the material was fully regenerated, confirming that low grade heat can regenerate CALF-20. From an energetic viewpoint, the reduction of purge flow at 70 °C

compensated the increase in temperature, being the least energy demanding among the three temperatures evaluated in this work.

Conclusions

Due to the low CO₂ concentration, the efficient removal and concentration of CO₂ from atmospheric air is a challenge. To achieve the ambitious goal of engineering energy efficient DAC processes, an appropriate adsorption material is pivotal. CALF-20, a recent hydrophobic MOF, shows promising results when used in a temperature swing adsorption process. Further studies in purification of the extracted carbon dioxide are required to achieve a low energy process. Furthermore, arranging CALF-20 in monoliths allows to reduce pressure drops across a contactor bed without compromising the energy efficiency of the whole DAC process.

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